

TRANSLATION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING

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This article focuses in teaching English on the base of translation. The authors show the global approach to the translation methodology, practical tools, the role of grammar in translation and principles of translation. At the same time they explain the aim of translation as a cross cultural bilingual communication vehicle among peoples.

Keywords: communicative approach, interaction, unconsciously, terminology, language teaching, grammar translation, influence.

Translation has always played a role in language teaching. Until the end of the eighteenth century, learning a foreign language implied learning Latin and was based around bi-lingual word lists and parallel texts. When 'modern' languages began to be taught at the end of the century, the same approach was followed, and the structures of English, French, Italian and so on were presented in relation to the structure of Latin. Speaking was not the aim of learning the language: the focus was on the translation of model sentences, chosen to exemplify the structural idiosyncrasies of the language system.

This approach became known as the *Grammar Translation* method, since students were presented with rules and then applied them in translation. The theoretical underpinning was "memorizing rules and facts in order to understand and manipulate the morphology and the syntax of the foreign language". The importance of structure in this approach has resulted in the view that translation is unpedagogical and uncommunicative, which still persists today. The 'Communicative Approach', which most teachers today would profess to use (in some form or other) in the classroom is ambiguous in its approach to translation. Purists argue that all interaction should be undertaken in the L2, although some advocates claim that translation can and should be used (judiciously) in class. Howatt (in Richards and Rodgers, 1986), for example, writes: "translation may be used where students need or benefit from it." Other approaches which use LI in practice include 'Community Language Learning' (where students are provided with language after saying it in the mother tongue) and 'Suggestopaedia' (where learners are frequently exposed to bi-lingual word-lists or parallel LI- L2 texts.[1]

A summary of translation theory and problems translation poses

There is a great deal of theory behind the different concepts of translation. We will now consider some of the issues central to the translation process. It is worthwhile looking at these issues since we can confirm that the problems they give rise to are all apparent in my

learners' production. The errors they commit in speaking and writing are all unquestionably due to translating (often unconsciously) directly from their LI.[2]

Intercultural discourse

Translations include literary (prose, poetry, theatre), journalistic (economics, politics, current news), technical texts (urbanism, advertising, tourist guides, international organizations, etc.), so students are able to manage different kinds of special languages. Translation is a two-way device because a comparison between the two languages. Every text has its own terminology; even slang and everyday idioms characterize a text.

Students must keep a glossary, which they continuously update. Writing down words in a notebook allows the student to exercise his/her memory. Students are also taught how to read a dictionary, including the phonetic alphabet in order to learn the exact pronunciation. They usually undervalue the resources provided by a dictionary and often glance at it superficially.[3] The students use both bilingual and monolingual dictionaries. Bilingual ones (even the best) are often inadequate: sometimes there are imperfections or they might lead to the wrong meaning.

Moreover, paying attention to etymology is another strategy that helps them memorize and understand the real meaning of that word in its context and co-text. Each word in a text belongs to what is around it on a micro- and macro-level, and the analysis of each lexical unit allows the so-called "disambiguation," thus clarifying the effective meaning of a term within a passage.

Practical tools

By preparing a curriculum vitae (CV) or a cover letter in English, students realize that translating is not only a job, but something that involves their lives, their everyday experience and is not a mechanical action. When translating a CV they must keep cultural differences, as well as differences in educational systems and job titles in mind. They realize that a degree or a job position cannot be simply translated. Students are directed and encouraged at the same time to search on the

Internet: this represents not only an exercise in localization but also in the use of the web in English, thus learning terminology and practicing the English language. And if they make the decision of working as translators in the future they will be more familiar with computers and more skillful when using CAT.[4]

The role of grammar

By starting from grammar, students can reach higher level of translation and, vice-versa, by translating they acquire more competence in the knowledge of grammatical structures. Translation is cultural mediation. A comparison between two cultures allows the students to familiarize themselves with the linguistic elements that are unavoidably connected to their culture. Grammatical rules are the backbone of a language and cannot be ignored. During translation, but also working on parallel texts, it is possible to discover the role played by a grammatical rule and how it is actually applied. Some students have special difficulty in identifying the right tenses and translating them correctly. The discussion of an entire translated passage or even of one word in classroom teaches the students that a word usually does not have just one possible translation. Students learn that every word assumes a different meaning according to the context.

Translating cannot be separated from interpreting, even when we speak about a written text. The purpose of both is to transfer information from the SL to the TL[5]. Interpreting can serve as a mental exercise to improve the students speaking skills, although they will still need to practice conversation.

Classroom translation exercise

As a first approach, it is useful to translate short sentences in order to be able to build a longer paragraph and deepen the structure of the single phrase later on. As pointed out above, grammar is the basis of learning a language. A word-for-word back-translation enables the student to highlight the relationship between the two languages. L1 and L2 have different structures.

Back-translation involves mainly the syntactical structure, rather than only the lexical level; it is a comparison between the patterns of the two languages where individual lexical units may or may not match. It is possible to understand the sentence on a logical level and consequently convey the meaning in the L2. This exercise entails interpreting a text and the awareness that losses, gains, compensations, omissions and shifts often occur in translation. In English there is the immediacy not only in the verb but also in the adverb "now". Formal correspondence does not exist, while textual equivalence does. Translation structure, students are forced to pay attention to other elements that exclusively belong to the L2.[6]

Parallel translation is not always possible, not only for reasons of grammar, but also for socio-cultural reasons. A free translation becomes a useful tool to point out aspects of a culture, and consequently to master a language.

Many English teachers associate translation activities with grammar translation as a method. Teachers feel, with some justification, that:

- it is text-bound

- it is not a communicative activity (because it involves no oral interaction)
- time-consuming (not suitable for work in the classroom-because students must do the writing on their own)
- use of the mother tongue is required (but it is not desirable at the
- English lessons)
- it is boring - both to do, and to correct

This may be so, but many other approaches are possible. Translation can be introduced, purposefully, into the language learning programme.

In the book Alan Duff highlights at least 5 reasons for using translation in the classroom:

1. Influence of the mother tongue.

We all have mother tongue, or the 1st language, or the language of habitual use- in the interpretation by Peter Newmark. It shapes our way of thinking and our use of the foreign language to some extent. Translation helps us to understand better the influence of one language on the other. And, because translation involves contrast, it enables us to explore the potential of both languages- their strengths and weaknesses.

2. Naturalness of the activity.

Translation is a natural and necessary activity. Outside the classroom- in airports, offices, banks, etc.- translation is going on all the time. Why not inside the classroom?

3. The skill aspect.

Language competence is a two-way system. We need to be able to communicate both ways: into and from the foreign language. Translation is a perfect means for practicing this vital skill.

4. The reality of language.

The proper material for translation is authentic and wide-ranging: the learner is being brought into touch with the whole language, and not just the parts isolated by the textbooks.

5. Usefulness.

As a language learning activity, translation has a lot of merits:

- It invites speculation and discussion. In translation there is hardly any 'right' answer, but there are a lot of wrong ones. Doing all the work individually and in writing is not necessary. Students can work in pairs or groups for oral discussion. You may choose short texts for reading and discussion to save the time.

- Translation develops three essential qualities to all language learning: *accuracy, clarity and flexibility*. It trains the reader to search (flexibility) for the most appropriate words (accuracy) to convey what is meant (clarity).[7]

- Depending on the students' needs, and on the syllabus, the teacher can select material to illustrate particular aspects of language and structures the students have difficulty with. By working through these difficulties in the mother tongue, the students can see the link between the language (grammar) and usage.

- Translators will always be needed. Without them, there would be no summit talks, no Olympic Games, no international festivals and so on. And who is to do this work? - Either the professionals, or the students of language.

Professional translation is a specialized skill that requires specialized training. And, actually, it is not the goal we would like to achieve. The goal of translation is more like to provide learning opportunities in the process of creating translations and examination of them as final products in order to develop language awareness. Translation activities should be used in the English classroom, and they should be supported by communicative, natural learning methods.

Material for translating:

Selecting the material for the work, a teacher tries to take into consideration the following criteria:

- it should reflect the students' needs and be appropriate to their level.

- it should be authentic (press, books, Internet)
- it should represent full range of styles and registers.

- it should illustrate the problems, challenges and strategies of translation in general.

- it should be interesting and translatable.

The length of the texts is also important: short texts for oral work in class, and longer ones for translation at home (mostly in writing)

Principles of translation

Here are some guidelines on how to help the students evaluate their own work. The principles are adapted from Frederick Fuller: *The Translator's Handbook*.

meaning	The translation should reflect accurately the meaning of the original text. Ask yourself: - is the meaning of the original text clear? <i>if not</i> , where does the uncertainty lie? - are any words 'loaded', that is, are there any underlying implications? - Is the dictionary meaning of a particular word the most suitable one?
form	The ordering of words and ideas in the translation should match the original as closely as possible. (This is particularly important in translating legal documents, guarantees, contracts, etc.) But differences in language structure often require, changes in the form and order of words.
register	Languages often differ greatly in their levels of formality in a given context. Consider: - would any expression in the original sound too formal/informal, cold/warm, personal/impersonal... if translated literally? - What is the intention of the speaker or writer? (to persuade/dissuade, apologize/criticize?) Does this come through in the translation?
source language influence	One of the most frequent criticisms of translation is that it doesn't sound natural'. A good way of shaking off the source language (SL) influence is not set the text aside and translate a few sentences aloud, from memory. This will suggest natural patterns of thought in the target language (TL), which may not come to mind when the eye is fixed on the SL text.
style and clarity	The translator should not change the style of the original. But if the text is sloppily written, or full of tedious repetitions, the translator may, for the reader's sake, correct the defects.
idiom	Idiomatic expressions are notoriously untranslatable. If the expressions cannot be directly translated, try any of the specific methods of transferring the meaning of the idioms. The golden rule is: if the idiom does not work in the TL., do not force it into the translation.

Correction:

Much of the correction is done by the students themselves during oral discussions at the lesson:

- they listen to each other, they are more receptive to any corrections (students learn from each other's mistakes)

- the teacher doesn't have to correct the same errors several times (it always happens with written translation). One comment is quite enough for the whole group.

But it doesn't mean that the correction of written works should be rejected. Translation in writing must be done and it needs correcting. Correction might be the opportunity to encourage: marking not only errors, but also underlining felicitous solutions.

Taking into consideration all what was mentioned above:

- short and varied texts for work in the class
- equal involvement in the task
- as much oral translation as possible
- writing only in the form of notes, to be used in later discussions
- time limits where necessary
- pair and group interaction

Is translation, actually, time-consuming? I think, not.

Is it non-communicative? I think, not.

Does it give the opportunities to develop language awareness? I think, yes/

And I'd like to reformulate *teaching translation* into *using translation*.

Conclusion

Teaching translation can be a useful tool and an effective method to learn language. Translation can be a very valuable classroom activity. It is especially beneficial in the monolingual classroom and can be tailored in such a way that is highly practical, learner-focused and process-based. It seems to us that translation can be highly effective way of drawing learners attention to the linguistic, semantic and pragmatic features of the target language. In the classroom then, when we use translation as a technique, there are number of strategies we can usefully adopt. They are:

1. To make students more aware of the equivalent affect of what they translate
2. To ensure that texts used are interesting, relevant and as far as possible, authentic. Using shorter texts in the classrooms and longer ones at home which can then be discussed will maximise the time spent in class and will encourage spontaneous speech, negotiations and discussion.

3. To make translation a process-based activity, including all students at all stages of the process. This will include giving time to plan, reflect, discuss, review and edit their work, and also encourage meaningful, independent interaction in English

4. To try and provide students with learner-centered, cognitive translation activities to help them notice the differences between LI and L2 meaning patterns and of the language system as a whole.

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